

**ANALYSIS OF CHANGES IN THE DISTRIBUTION OF THE GREAT (RHOMBOMYS OPIMUS)
AND OTHER SANDFLIES IN THE ANTHROPOGENICALLY MODIFIED AREA OF THE
BALKHASH-ALAKOL BASIN**

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ABSTRACT

On the basis of study and analysis of literature sources, report data of plague control stations, collections from the museum of 'M. Aikimbayev NSCEOI' and own collections in natural foci of plague, new data on the current state of fauna and peculiarities of ecology and distribution of rodent species - carriers of plague pathogens in Southern Pribalkhashye were obtained. New data on the distribution and abundance of major and minor carriers of the plague pathogen were obtained.

Cartographic materials of internet resources Bing, Yandex, Google on anthropogenic change of landscapes in desert plague foci located on the territory of Balkhash-Alakol basin were studied, data of anti-epidemic units of the station were analysed, observations of zoologists (including their own data) and scientific materials of literature sources on the distribution of the great gerbil (*Rhombomys opimus*) and other carriers of especially dangerous infections in the anthropogenically modified territory of the Pribalkhash, Taukum, Iliysk intermountain and Pribalkhol autonomous plague foci were analysed. The changes were analysed for the last five years.

Keywords: rodents, especially dangerous infections, plague, great gerbil, carriers of plague pathogen, natural plague center.

Problem statement. There is active construction of motorways, oil pipelines, high-voltage power lines, recreation centres and reserves in the Pribalkhash area, which leads to changes in the landscape and affects the rodent population. Reconstruction of the motorway Taldykorgan-Lepsy - Balkhash lake will lead to dispersal of rodents. Reconstruction of the Taldykorgan-Lepsy-Balkhash motorway will lead to dispersal of the greater sand lance along embankments and settlement of new territories. The construction of high-voltage power lines and oil pipelines and the construction of the Pribalkhash reserve will lead to a local increase in the population of the greater sand lance.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. Against the background of intensification of water consumption in China and Kazakhstan, the problem of preserving aquatic and near-water ecosystems of Lake Balkhash, one of the largest water bodies of the Republic of Kazakhstan, is becoming increasingly clear [1-3].

Shallowing of Lake Balkhash will affect natural plague foci located in the south-east of the RK. It may lead to irreversible climate changes (temperature regime, precipitation, air and soil humidity), which may have an unfavourable impact on the biocapacity and stability of mammalian populations and, in particular, on populations of carriers of pathogens of particularly dangerous infections [4-6]. In the Southern Pribalkhash region, the greater sandfly is a background species [7-9]. It is the most widespread rodent, with family burrows-colonies distributed almost throughout the entire territory with a density of 0.5 to 4.5 per 1 ha and a colony diameter of 20-50 m or more. This animal is highly sensitive and susceptible to the plague pathogen and is its main carrier [10-12]. In the Southern Pribalkhash region there are three large autonomous plague foci, which are part of the Central Asian desert natural plague foci - the Taukum and Pribalkhash desert foci and the Ili intermountain foci, which are currently the most active in the country. Between the Pribalkhash

and Ili intermountain foci there is the Dzungarian mountain foci, which are part of the Tien Shan mountain natural plague foci, where one of the main carriers is the grey marmot (*Marmota baibacina*). In the other listed foci, the main carrier of plague (*Yersinia pestis*) is the great gerbil (*Rhombomys opimus*). This species is key in desert and semi-desert habitats. Taking into account the family-colonial lifestyle of the Greater Sandpiper, the presence of complex burrow colonies, and active swarming activity, it is a landscape-forming species. The rich fauna of ectoparasites in the burrows of the great gerbil and their visit by almost all animals that are potential carriers of plague infection create favourable conditions for interspecific exchange of ectoparasites [13-15].

Highlighting of previously unresolved parts of the general problem. As a result of reconstruction of the Almaty-Astana road within the Taukum hotspot in the construction right-of-way there is destruction of settlements of both great and red-tailed gerbils. As practice shows, after completion of works, the number of rodents along the road will be restored within a short time. The increase in the number of recreation centres (hunting, fishing) near Lake Balkhash has led to the formation of large dumps and changes in the relief of the territory and their settlement by the greater sand lance. The red-tailed gerbil inhabited the ruins of buildings of Aksuek settlement with high density. The impact of the anthropogenically altered area on changes in the populations of the Greater and Lesser Sandpipers requires detailed study.

Purpose of the article. To analyse changes in the distribution of great and other small sandflies in the anthropogenically modified territory of the Balkhash-Alakol basin

Summary of the main material. In recent years, significant anthropogenic changes of landscapes have taken place in the hotspots. Gas pipelines with infrastructural facilities (pumping stations, road along the gas pipeline) passing through the territory of the hotspots have been constructed and put into operation, new motorways and railway lines have been laid. Old motorways are being reconstructed. New settlements have been built, construction of infrastructure facilities in the border zone continues, the area of natural landscapes is being reduced by expanding the borders of settlements, construction of new recreation centres, etc. The changes entail an increase in the number of temporary and permanent population. In some cases there is degradation of rural settlements due to the outflow of population to cities and destruction of houses. All this leads to a change in the nature of the presence of carriers of CWD in the transformed territory. If at the moment of construction there is degradation of rodent settlements and even disappearance of separate local populations, then later on there is often development of anthropogenically modified territories by rodents with behavioural changes and adaptation to the permanent human presence.

Ili intermountain focus. Sandpipers (Greater, Pomarine and Red-tailed Sandpipers) from the immediate vicinity of the natural landscape inhabited the sites of

the earlier gas pipeline within 1-2 years. Around pumping stations, power substations and simply left terrain changes (piles of soil, ditches), the density of densities of Greater and Red-tailed Sandpipers is noticeably higher than in the natural surrounding landscape. On the embankments of the new road and railway, the Greater Sandpiper began to inhabit the immediate vicinity a year after construction was completed. This rodent has moved up to one kilometre along the elevated embankment into meadow areas where it had not previously burrowed. It builds colonies along the entire height of the embankment, with individual outcrops dug at the very edge of the hard pavement. The use of fine-mesh plastic netting to prevent wind erosion of soil during railway construction does not stop the development of embankments by the Greater Sandpiper. They can easily chew through this mesh when making their burrows. On road sections on loess and clay soils, Red-tailed Sandpipers also inhabit embankments if there are suitable settlements around them. When landscapes are changed in large areas (construction of new settlements and large infrastructure facilities), where sandflies used to inhabit, there is no rapid development of these areas by rodents. This phenomenon was observed in the Khorgos border zone, where only sporadic colonies of the Greater Sandpiper and Red-tailed Sandpiper colonies have appeared in the last five years. As a result of irregular construction of civil facilities during the expansion of settlements, the remaining areas of natural landscape with settlements of the Greater and Red-tailed Sandpiper are included in the settlements.

Prialakolskiy focus. No major anthropogenic landscape changes have occurred within the focus area in recent years. Settlements of the Greater Sandpiper have been preserved within the previously known boundaries. After completion of reconstruction of the Usharal-Dostyk motorway along the embankment, it is possible to move it westwards. The Red-tailed Sandpiper, which is widespread throughout the whole territory of the focus area, in recent years has moved outside the focus area and reached the recreation centres in Akshi village along the modified terrain along Lake Alakol.

Taukumskiy focus. As a result of the reconstruction of the Almaty-Astana road within the hearth in the construction strip there is destruction of settlements of both great and red-tailed gerbils. As practice shows, after completion of works, the number of rodents along the road will be restored within a short time.

The increase in the number of recreation centres (hunting, fishing) near Lake Balkhash has led to the formation of large dumps and changes in the relief of the territory and their settlement by the greater sand lance.

The Red-tailed Sandpiper inhabited the ruins of buildings of Aksuek settlement with high density.

Pribalkhash focus. In this hotspot, motorways, oil pipelines, high-voltage power lines, recreation centres and reserves have been or are being actively constructed, which leads to changes in the landscape and affects the rodent population. Reconstruction of the Taldykorgan-Lepsey-Lake Balkhash motorway will lead to the dispersal of the greater sand lance on embankments and settlement of new territories. The construction of high-voltage power lines and oil pipelines

and the construction of the Pribalkhash reserve will lead to a local increase in the population of the greater sand lance.

Conclusions and suggestions. Anthropogenic changes in the landscape, especially in narrow localities (roads, gas and oil pipelines, etc.), do not lead to the degradation of settlements of CWD carriers, and in some cases, on the contrary, to an increase in the density of settlements and their number. Increased migration of temporary and permanent population, as well as maintenance of erected infrastructure facilities leads to an increased risk of PLOI infection, which increases the epidemic potential of the territory.

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